

"MODERN DIAGNOSTIC METHODS OF SLEEP DISORDERS IN PRIMARY HEADACHES"

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ANNOTATION

In the article, various sleep disorders observed in primary headaches (Migraine, Cluster headache, Tension headache), insomnia, modern examination methods, their prevalence among the population and preventive measures the measure is to develop activities.

Key words: Primary headaches, dyscirculatory encephalopathy, sleep disorder, polysomnography, modern diagnostics.

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada Birlamchi bosh og'riqlar ya'ni (Migren, Klaster bosh og'rig'i, Zo'riqish bosh og'rig'i) larida kuzatiladigan turli xildagi uyqu buzilishlari, uyqusizlik, zamonaviy tekshiruv usullari, ularning aholi orasi tarqalganlik darajasi va profilaktik chora tadbirlarni ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Birlamchi bosh og'riqlari, dissirkulyator entsefalopatiya, uyqu buzilishi, polisomnografiya, zamonaviy diagnostika.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассмотрены различные нарушения сна, наблюдаемые при первичных головных болях (мигрень, кластерная головная боль, головная боль напряжения), инсомниях, современные методы обследования, их распространенность среди населения и меры профилактики, меры по развитию деятельности.

Ключевые слова: первичные головные боли, дисциркуляторная энцефалопатия, нарушение сна, полисомнография, современная диагностика.

Relevance: In this article, we will focus on modern methods of examination of sleep disorders observed in primary headaches. According to statistics, about 90% of people experience a headache at least once a year. About 1.7 - 4% of the world's population suffers from headaches that last 15 days or more every month. Sleep disturbance is one of the factors for evaluating the quality of human life. Insomnia is observed in 25% of men and 50% of elderly women. More than 25% of patients use sleeping pills regularly or frequently. The prevalence of sleep disorders in the general population ranges from 6 to 30%, depending on the diagnostic method. About 30% of people over the age of 55 suffer from insomnia.

Sleep disorders lead to the abuse of sleeping pills and increase the risk of traffic accidents. Insomnia patients have been shown to have a 2.5-4.5 times higher risk of having an accident than healthy people. The working capacity of patients suffering from insomnia is 2 times lower than that of healthy people. Decreased attention and reaction speed in patients suffering from insomnia increases the risk of accidents at work. Polysomnography is a modern instrumental method of diagnosing sleep disorders. Polysomnographic study - long-term (for example, day and night) monitoring of various physiological functions during sleep. Full and healthy sleep is the key to good health for the whole day. It is at night that the most

important processes of replenishing energy reserves and renewing cells take place in the body. Unfortunately, in some cases (under stress, chronic pathologies, etc.), a person loses the ability to sleep well. Various disorders lead to a bad state during the day, decreased performance, constant fatigue, irritability, etc. To determine the causes of such disorders, polysomnography (polysomnographic study) is conducted - a comprehensive diagnosis of the sleeping person's body. What is a polysomnographic examination and what is its purpose? This examination method is aimed at determining the causes of sleep disorders. During the inspection, the specialist can get valuable information about all deviations from the norm and identify violations. Modern high-precision devices - electrodes and sensors - are used to correct body signals. They are installed on certain parts of the patient's body. Data from sensors is processed and recorded. After that, the information is analyzed by a somnologist and makes it possible to make an accurate diagnosis.

The research is absolutely safe and non-invasive method. Therefore, it is recommended for people with chronic diseases, pregnant women and even children.

This method of examination is performed all night long, until waking up. Therefore, the diagnosis is carried out in a hospital with a special room. It should be understood that in some cases the examination will last a long time, the patient must get used to new conditions. Therefore, the diagnosis can be carried out not in one, but in several nights.

The technique is non-invasive, does not damage the integrity of the skin and does not require the use of drugs. Therefore, the study has no contraindications. The patient does not feel any pain when installing the sensors and during sleep. The study does not cause complications. Therefore, polysomnography can be used for patients of any gender and age.

The purpose of the study: improvement of modern examination methods for sleep disorders in primary headaches, assessment of quality of life by mutual comparison of sleep disorders among patients treated with primary headaches and discirculatory encephalopathy stage I-II cephalic syndrome.

Research materials and methods:

With the help of modern examinations, a diagnostic examination was carried out in order to determine sleep disorders in 50 groups of patients aged 18-55 with the diagnosis of primary headaches and discirculatory encephalopathy stage I-II cephalic syndrome. Polysomnography modern examination is used to determine comparative levels of sleep disorders in patients suffering from the diagnosis of primary and discirculatory encephalopathy stage I-II cephalic syndrome on the basis of diagnostic tests Table 1

According to polysomnography examination:

1-Table

Results of the study: So it can be seen that when we conducted a polysomnography examination to detect sleep disorders, 20 of the 30 primary headache patients had sleep disorders. In groups of 20 patients with discirculatory encephalopathy I-II stage cephalic syndrome, this indicator was 9.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be said that sleep disturbance in primary headache discirculatory encephalopathy was a high indicator of sleep disturbance in the group of patients with cephalic syndrome of stage I-II.

Thus, early diagnosis of sleep disorders in primary headaches is important for improving the patient's quality of life, maintaining work productivity, and starting early diagnostic tests can prevent insomnia.

Preventive measures in patients should be avoided in the first place from stress, psycho-emotional stress, various weather conditions, people working in various professions, especially those who work at night, should develop a daily routine, diet, diet and food should contain enough minerals and vitamins.

Various painkillers and sleeping pills give us temporary relief, but cannot eliminate the underlying cause.

Therefore, patients with headaches and various sleep disorders should see a specialist (Neurologist, Somnologist) and get the necessary recommendations.

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